

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

Education

A STUDY ON TEMPERAMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH REGARD TO GENDER

KEY WORDS: Temperament, Higher secondary students, t-test, random sampling method

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ABSTRACT The main aim of the present study is to investigate the temperament of higher secondary students with regard to gender. The investigator used the survey method of research. The investigator used the temperament Scale (2016). It is a self-made tool which is standardized and validated by the investigator. The sample for present study consists of 299 higher secondary students from 10 schools of Sivagiri Taluk selected by random sampling method. The investigator used mean, standard deviation and t-test for descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. From the result of inferential analysis, the investigator found that there is significant difference in temperament of higher secondary students with regard to gender.

INTRODUCTION

Personality development refers “to the gradual development of characteristic emotional responses or temperament, a recognizable style of life, personal roles and role behaviours, a set of values and goals. Typical patterns of adjustment, characteristic interpersonal relations and sexual relationships characteristic traits and a relatively fixed self-image. In other world, ‘personality development is the development of the organized pattern of behaviour and attitude that makes a person distinctive. by the ongoing interaction of temperament, character and environment. Hence, if all the three dimensions namely emotional, Physical and intellectual are given equal importance then it is called total development of personality. Temperament is one of the dimensions in personality. Temperament is an essential quality of the total personality. It is a disposition within the person to respond to emotional stimuli and situations and to express himself emotionally in a unique manner. Temperament is simply the emotional life of a person, but his emotional life is always conditioned by the person’s unique affective disposition.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Temperament is perhaps the single most important attribute and the key to understanding the behavior of an individual. This world today consists as both the best of times and the worst of times for adolescents. Adolescence is the transition period from childhood to adulthood. One can encounter stress and storm during this period due to physical emotional, intellectual and social change. The concentration diversion would also be the result if they are not trained properly. To flourish in the academic aspect the children should prepare all efforts to study systematically. The external diversion should also be controlled to provide children conducive environment for their study. Researchers have found that both temperaments play a greater role in the live of adolescents. On the one hand temperament helps the adolescents to respond to emotional stimuli and situations and to express themselves emotionally in a unique manner and on the other hand temperament assists in changing or modifying their behavior. For the present investigation the temperament of higher secondary students are taken into consideration. It is taken in that sense that the students represent a period of intensive growth and changes in nearly all aspects of child’s physical mental, social and emotional life. The growth achieved, the experience gained, responsibilities felt and the relationships developed at this stage destine the complete factor of an individual. The children who are studying in higher secondary aim at maintaining their temperament at any costs whenever possible, they try to impress their peers with their status. This helps the students to bloom in their life with his backdrop a study is taken to analyze the temperament of higher secondary students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the level of temperament of higher secondary school with regard to gender.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in

Temperament of higher secondary school students with respect to background variables such as class, gender,

TOOL USED

The temperament scale (2016) was standardized and validated by the investigator.

POPULATION

According to John W.Best and James V.Kahn (1986) “A population is any group of individuals that have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher”. The population for present study was all the higher secondary students in Sivagiri Educational District.

SAMPLE

A small portion of population selected for observation is called a sample. The investigator for has randomly selected 299 higher secondary students in Sivagiri educational district for the present study. Totally ten schools were taken for the study. The sampling technique used in the study is random sampling method.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DATA

To find out the level of temperament of higher secondary school students with regard to gender.

Table - 1 The level of temperament of higher secondary school students with regard to gender

Gender	Low		Average		High	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Male	94	61.0	40	26.0	20	13
Female	60	41.4	55	37.9	30	20.7

It is inferred from the above table, with regard to male, 61.0% of higher secondary school students have low level , 26.0% of them have average level and 13% of them have high level of temperament. With regard to female 41.4 higher secondary school students have low level, 37.9% of them have average level and 20.7% of them have high level of temperament.

INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF DATA

H0 1: There is no significant difference in temperament of higher secondary school students with regard to gender.

Table - 2 't' test showing significant difference in temperament of higher secondary school students with regard to gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Tabulated 't' value	Remark
Temperament	Male	154	77.9545	8.19241	3.817	1.96	S
	Female	145	81.3931	7.32793			

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (3.817) is greater than the table value (1.96) for df (297) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence then null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in temperament of higher secondary school students with regard to gender.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The result of t-test showed that there is significant difference in temperament of higher secondary school students with respect to gender. The mean difference revealed that the female higher secondary students have greater temperament than the male higher secondary students. The reason could be that the girls are exposed to different life situations and this knowledge helps them to tackle the problems efficiently. Guidance and counseling programmes may be conducted in schools to make the students to be aware of their own emotions and how to manage them.

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